

A case series of mullerian duct anomalies – The Diagnostic Journey

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ABSTRACT:

Mullerian duct anomalies are rare affecting approximately 1% females with 3% having poor reproductive outcome. These congenital anomalies result due to failure of formation or failure of fusion of the mullerian ducts. According to the American Fertility Society (AFS), the mullerian duct anomalies are classified into seven different categories. Ultrasound is the first imaging investigation in cases of suspected mullerian anomalies while MRI is the key imaging modality of choice due to its capabilities of demonstrating the female genital tract remarkably well and ability to provide the details of intra-uterine anatomy, external fundal contour and its ability of imaging of entire female pelvis into multiple imaging planes. Also, it provides additional information about the other associated anomalies particularly those of urinary system and helps in differentiating other causes of amenorrhea.

In this study, we review the key imaging features of anomalies of formation and fusion of mullerian ducts with their classification into different categories based on the imaging features.

Keywords: Mullerian duct anomalies (MDAs), Ultrasound (US), Hysterosalpingography (HSG), Magnetic resonance imaging (MRI), infertility, amenorrhea, renal agenesis.

INTRODUCTION:

Mullerian duct anomalies have a profound impact on the reproductive health of a woman. Prevalence of mullerian duct anomaly is high among women with infertility and frequent miscarriages. Prevalence of MDAs is 5.5% in general population; however, the prevalence is higher in infertile women (8%) and even higher in women with miscarriages (13.3 to 24.5%) [1], [2]. Embryologically, two paired mesonephric (wolffian) ducts and paramesonephric (mullerian) ducts appear at 6th week of gestation. The growth and fusion of two paramesonephric ducts with simultaneous regression of mesonephric ducts occur in female fetus due to absence of mullerian inhibiting factor (MIF). Mullerian duct anomalies result in failure of formation or midline fusion of the mullerian ducts [3].

Clinically, the patients with mullerian anomalies present with primary amenorrhea with or without cyclical pain, abnormal uterine bleeding, dysmenorrhea, hematometra in cases of obstructed vagina, recurrent pregnancy loss, cervical incompetence, intrauterine growth restriction or intrauterine fetal demise, malpresentations, placental

abruption or rarely pregnancy in the rudimentary horn. Obstructive uterine anomalies are associated with hematometra, retrograde menstruation and endometriosis.

Mullerian anomalies are associated with urinary tract anomalies including renal agenesis, horseshoe kidney, duplication of collecting system, renal dysplasia or ectopic kidney. Renal agenesis is the most commonly reported anomaly, occurring in 67% of cases [4]. Renal anomalies occur in 29% of patients with MDAs and most commonly associated with unicornuate uteri. They are reported in approximately 40% patients with unicornuate uteri [4], [5].

Ultrasound is the first investigation in the females presenting with primary amenorrhea, infertility or recurrent miscarriage. It is quick, easily available, economical and lacks radiation. However, image degradation can occur with large patients, overlying bowel gas, and the external contour may be difficult to visualize. Three-dimensional (3D) ultrasound is a new technique which is more accurate than two-dimensional ultrasound and equal or better than MRI at assessing MDA [7]. Hysterosalpingography (HSG) allows for assessment of the uterine cavity and tubal

patency but is limited at visualizing the external uterine contour. MRI is the definitive diagnostic tool as it provides detailed delineation of these anomalies due to its multiplanar imaging abilities. It lacks radiation and provides clear delineation of both the internal and the external uterine anatomy. Furthermore, MRI clearly defines the entire pelvic anatomy in females helping in detecting associated anomalies particularly those of urinary system

The purpose of this study is to review the embryology, classification, imaging features and treatment options of mullerian anomalies and their illustration using ultrasound and MRI.

DISCUSSION:

Embryologically, two paired mesonephric (wolffian) ducts and two paired paramesonephric (mullerian) ducts appear at sixth week of gestation. Due to absence of mullerian inhibiting factor (MIF), bidirectional

growth of mullerian ducts with simultaneous regression of mesonephric ducts occur. This growth is accompanied by midline migration and fusion of mullerian ducts with eventual resorption of the intervening septum, resulting in the development of the fallopian tubes, uterus and upper 2/3 of vagina. Abnormality in any of these processes result in certain mullerian anomaly according to the stage of development[2], [3], [5].

American Society of Reproductive Medicine (ASRM) (formerly known as American Fertility Society-AFS) classification of mullerian duct anomalies is the most commonly used and widely accepted classification system which was published in 1988[10], revising the work done by Buttram and Gibbons in 1979[11]. It divides the mullerian duct anomalies into seven different categories as follows:

Class I- Mullerian agenesis / hypoplasia:

CASE 1:

A 15-year-old female patient presented with complaints of primary amenorrhoea subjected to USG (Figure 1).

Figure-1: USG demonstrated absent uterus (image 2) with empty right renal fossa and absent right kidney (image 1).

Patient was followed-up with MRI (Figure 2).

Figure-2: MRI showed complete agenesis of uterus and vagina (image 3 showing empty uterine fossa) however bilateral ovaries were normal (images 4 and 5). A diagnosis of Myer-Rokitansky-Kuster-Hauser Syndrome was made.

CASE 2:

A 29-year-old female patient presented with complaints of primary amenorrhea (Figure 3).

Figure-3: USG and MRI demonstrated hypoplastic uterus and cervix with poorly differentiated zonal anatomy. A diagnosis of Class I Mullerian anomaly was made.

Early developmental failure at 5th weeks of gestation results in agenesis or hypoplasia of uterus, cervix and upper 2/3rd of vagina[12]. In agenesis, uterus is absent or a small amount of rudimentary undifferentiated tissue can be seen. The most common form is Myer-Rokitansky-Kuster-Hauser syndrome[13], [14]. These patients present with primary amenorrhea with normal development of secondary sexual characters, as ovaries are normal. In uterine hypoplasia, small differentiated organ is present.

Class II – Unicornuate uterus:

CASE 3:

A 23-year-old female patient came with complaints of infertility and abdominal pain (Figure 4)

Figure-4: HSG demonstrated uterine cavity deviated to right side. No endometrial widening near the fundus was noted... a case of unicornuate uterus.

CASE 4:

A 24-year-old female patient presented with complaints of infertility (Figure 5).

Figure-5: MRI demonstrated leftward oriented T2W/STIR hyperintense structure abutting the left ovary (red arrows) communicating with a hypoplastic vagina. No endometrial widening near fundus was noted. Bilateral ovaries were normal (green arrows in image 3 and image 5). No obvious rudimentary horn was noted on right side. A diagnosis of unicornuate configuration of the uterus was given.

Unicornuate uterus results from agenesis or hypoplasia of one of the müllerian ducts. It has one functioning uterine horn, single fallopian tube with a normal appearing cervix. It is further divided into four subtypes i.e. a) absent rudimentary horn, b) non-cavitary (non-functional) rudimentary horn, c) cavitary communicating rudimentary horn and d) cavitary non-communicating rudimentary horn[15]. Unicornuate uterus is most commonly associated with renal anomalies usually ipsilateral to the anomalous side.

Class III – Uterus didelphys:

CASE 5:

A 26-year-old female patient came with complaints of infertility (Figure 6).

Figure-6: USG and HSG demonstrated two divergent uterine horns with two cervixes with a large fundal cleft.

Patient was followed up with MRI (Figure 7).

Figure-7: MRI demonstrated two separate uterine horns with divergent apices and no evidence of communication in between, two separate cervixes and upper 2/3rd of vagina. Normal zonal anatomy was seen in both the uterine horns. A diagnosis of uterine didelphys was made.

Didelphic uterus results from complete non-fusion of mullerian ducts resulting in two separate uterine horns each communicating with ipsilateral fallopian tubes with two cervixes. Majority of the cases are associated with duplicated proximal 2/3rd of vagina and a longitudinal or a transverse vaginal septum may be present. Both uterine horns are normally developed and of normal size with wide separation making an obtuse angle and inter-cornual distance should be >4cm with deep fundal cleft. Didelphys uterus can present with the OHVIRA syndrome (obstructed hemi-vagina and associated ipsilateral renal agenesis) [16], [17].

Class IV – Bicornuate uterus:

CASE 6:

A 13-year-old female patient came with complaints of primary amenorrhea and cyclic pelvic pain (Figure 8).

Figure-8: USG demonstrated two uterine horns separated by a fundal cleft with a heterogeneously hypoechoic collection within the vaginal cavity.

Patient was followed-up with CT and MRI (Figure 9,10 and 11).

Figure-9: There were two separate uterine horns and cervical cavities opening into a single vaginal vault, separated by a fundal cleft measuring 1.6cm. the inter-cornual distance was 5cm with two uterine horns making an obtuse angle of 125°.

Figure-10: Right renal fossa was empty with non-visualization of right kidney into the right renal fossa or pelvis.

Figure-11: The vagina was distended by a T1W/T2W hyperintense collection extending into the cervix. No obvious vaginal septum was noted.

A diagnosis of bicornuate bicollis uterus with hematocolpos due to suspected imperforate hymen and right renal agenesis was made.

Bicornuate uterus results from partial non-fusion of the Mullerian ducts with central myometrium extending till internal cervical os (unicollis type) or till the level of external cervical os (bicollis type), with a deep fundal cleft $> 1\text{cm}$ [18]. It is commonly associated with normal vagina. The two uterine horns are not as fully developed as didelphys and are comparatively small in size, widely separated making an obtuse angle with inter-cornual distance $>4\text{cm}$. Bicornuate bicollis subtype should be differentiated from the didelphys uterus[19], [20], [21], [22].

Class V – Septate uterus:

CASE 7:

A 23-year-old female patient came with complaints of recurrent pregnancy loss (Figure 12).

Figure-12: USG demonstrated two endometrial cavities separated by a fundal cleft.

Patient was followed up with MRI (Figure 13).

Figure-13: MRI demonstrated two endometrial cavities separated by a T2W hypointense septum extending into the endocervical canal with normal fundal contour. The inter-cornual distance was 3.5 cm with an acute angle between two uterine cavities measuring 50°. A diagnosis of septate uterus was made.

Septate uterus results from the non-resorption of the septum between the completely fused müllerian ducts. As a result, uterus is partially or completely divided into two cavities by a septum which can be fibrous, muscular or both. Since the müllerian ducts are completely fused, it is associated with normal external fundal contour or even if the cleft is present, it is <1cm. It should be differentiated from bicornuate uterus as the both entities have different reproductive outcome. In septate uterus, inter-cornual distance is <4cm and the two endometrial cavities are divided by an acute angle usually <75°. Septate uterus can be associated with longitudinal vaginal septum [23]. Differentiation of the septum in fibrous or muscular is important as in case of fibrous septum, repair can be done by vaginal approach but in case of muscular septum, abdominal approach is required. Endometriosis is common in cases if septate uteri and has been documented in 30% of fertile and infertile women [24].

Class VI – Arcuate uterus:

CASE 8:

Figure-14: Incidentally detected arcuate uterus in a female patient underwent HSG after tubal recanalization(Figure 14).

It is the mildest form of the Mullerian anomalies and has been characterized as variant of the normal uterine anomaly or a uterus with small partial septum [25]. It results from near complete resorption of utero-vaginal septum. It is characterized by normal round external fundal contour or a small indentation at fundus can be present which is usually <1cm.

Cass VII – Diethylstilbestrol related Mullerian anomalies:

Diethylstilbestrol (DES) is a synthetic non-steroidal estrogen which was used previously to prevent miscarriage in high-risk patients. In utero exposure to DES results from uterine, vaginal and cervical malformations including hypoplasia or a T-shaped uterus. Features of T-shaped uterus are wide lower uterine segment, narrow fundal endometrial canal, irregular endometrial margins, and intraluminal endometrial filling defects. Cervical anomalies include hypoplasia, anterior cervical ridge, cervical collar and pseudo polyposis. Fallopian tube anomalies include a truncated appearance, saccular outpouchings, fimbria deformities.

Clinically, many females with MDAs are asymptomatic and a late diagnosis occurs during evaluation of infertility [26], [27]. Mullerian agenesis presents with primary amenorrhea. Women with obstructive anomaly presents with cyclical or non-cyclical pelvic pain. Obstructive anomalies are associated with hematometra, retrograde menstruation and can cause endometriosis [28], [29]. Females with MDAs can also present with abnormal bleeding and can be due to partial or micro-perforate vaginal obstruction or a longitudinal vaginal septum. In obstetrics, MDAs are associated with poor pregnancy outcome, recurrent pregnancy loss, intra-uterine growth restriction, preterm labor and delivery, malpresentations, placental abruption and intra-uterine fetal demise [30], [31], [32], [33].

Initial testing to evaluate pelvic anatomy includes hysteron-salpingography and two-dimensional ultrasound. HSG evaluates the tubal patency in women with infertility. In case of mullerian anomalies, HSG may identify patent canals and any abnormal communication. It can also demonstrate the patency of the rudimentary horn but is inadequate in evaluation of external uterine contour hence cannot reliably differentiate between various MDAs like bicornuate and septate uteri [18], [26], [34].

Ultrasound evaluation gives a brief idea about the uterine structure, endometrial contour, can detect a pelvic mass like hematometra and confirms the presence of ovaries and can be used to evaluate kidneys. When ultrasound is performed in secretory phase, better visualization of endometrium and internal uterine contour can be achieved[35], [36].Three-dimensional (3D) ultrasound is a new technique which is more accurate than two-dimensional ultrasound due to its ability to visualize the coronal section of uterus which helps in accurate delineation of endometrial cavity and uterine fundus and hence it is valuable in differentiating different MDAs [21], [39], [40].

MRI is the sensitive and specific imaging modality for Mullerian anomalies [18], [38]. It non-invasively provides the detailed intra-uterine anatomical details and additional information of the external uterine fundal contour which is important in differentiation between two major anomaly classes of septate and bicornuate/didelphys uterus [5], [6]and can identify if the rudimentary horn contains a functional

endometrium[18], [37]. MRI also delineates the detailed pelvic anatomy and also assesses renal morphology and location. It also helps in identifying other causes of amenorrhea such as androgen insensitivity syndrome in which rudimentary ectopic testes are present with absent uterus and ovaries [8], [9].

Mullerian anomalies are associated with urinary tract anomalies. Upper urinary tract anomalies include renal agenesis, horseshoe or pelvic kidney, duplication of collecting system or an ectopic ureter[41]. Renal anomalies are most common with uni-cornuate, didelphic uteri and mullerian agenesis [5] and are uncommon with bicornuate, septate and arcuate uteri[42]. In cases with obstructive mullerian anomalies, renal agenesis is common ipsilateral to the obstruction.

CONCLUSION:

Mullerian duct anomalies are complex and broad-spectrum developmental anomalies which can manifest variably both clinically as well as in imaging scenario. It can be detected initially at HSG during investigation of infertility and it provides information about the canal patency and any abnormal communications if present. US is usually the initial investigation in cases of primary amenorrhea, infertility and recurrent pregnancy loss and it provides brief information about the uterine structure, endometrial contour and the associated renal anomalies. MRI is the definitive investigation and the imaging modality of choice for identification and characterization of MDAs and also the investigation of choice in accurate delineation of the pelvic anatomy and detection of the associated urinary tract anomalies. Accurate identification of MDAs with correct differentiation is of utmost importance as the different classes of MDAs are associated with different reproductive outcomes and surgical management varies widely among the different subtypes.

REFERENCES:

1. Chan YY, Jayaprakasan K, Zamora J, Thornton JG, Raine-Fenning N, Coomarasamy A. The prevalence of congenital uterine anomalies in unselected and high-risk populations: a systematic review. *Hum Reprod Update*. 2011;17(6):761–771. doi: 10.1093/humupd/dmr028
2. Al Najjar MS, Al Ryalat NT, Sadaqah JS, Husami RY, Alzoubi KH. MRI Evaluation of Mullerian Duct Anomalies: Practical Classification by the New ASRM System. *J Multidiscip Healthc*. 2022 Nov 9;15:2579-2589. doi: 10.2147/JMDH.S386936. PMID: 36388626; PMCID: PMC9659481.
3. Marcal L, Nothaft MA, Coelho F, Volpato R, Iyer R. Mullerian duct anomalies: MR imaging. *Abdom Imaging*. 2011;36(6):756–764. doi: 10.1007/s00261-010-9681-x
4. Li S, Qayyam A, Coakley FV, Hricak H. Association of renal agenesis and Müllerian duct anomalies. *J Comput Assist Tomogr* 2000;6:829–34
5. Chandler TM, Machan LS, Cooperberg PL, Harris AC, Chang SD. Mullerian duct anomalies: from diagnosis to intervention. *Br J Radiol*. 2009 Dec;82(984):1034-42. doi: 10.1259/bjr/99354802. Epub 2009 May 11. PMID: 19433480; PMCID: PMC3473390.
6. Mueller GC, Hussain HK, Smith YR, Quint EH, Carlos RC, Johnson TD, et al. Müllerian duct anomalies: comparison of MRI diagnosis and clinical diagnosis. *AJR Am J Roentgenol*. 2007;189:1294–302
7. Deutch TD, Abuhamad AZ. The role of 3-dimensional ultrasonography and magnetic resonance imaging in the diagnosis of Müllerian duct anomalies. *J Ultrasound Med* 2008;27:413–23
8. Church DG, Vancil JM, Vasanawala SS. Magnetic resonance imaging for uterine and vaginal anomalies. *Curr Opin Obstet Gynecol*. 2009;21(5):379–389. doi: 10.1097/GCO.0b013e3283307c3e
9. Mueller GC, Hussain HK, Smith YR, et al. Müllerian duct anomalies: comparison of MRI diagnosis and clinical diagnosis. *AJR Am J Roentgenol*. 2007;189(6):1294–1302. doi: 10.2214/AJR.07.2494
10. Adhesions AD. The American Fertility Society classifications of adnexal adhesions, distal tubal occlusion, tubal occlusion secondary to tubal ligation, tubal pregnancies, müllerian anomalies and intrauterine adhesions. *Fertil Steril*. 1988;49(6):944–955. doi: 10.1016/S0015-0282(16)59942-7

11. Buttram VC Jr., Gibbons WE. Müllerian anomalies: a proposed classification. (An analysis of 144 cases). *Fertil Steril*. 1979;32(1):40–46. doi: 10.1016/S0015-0282(16)44114-2
12. Wang Y, Lu J, Zhu L, et al. Evaluation of Mayer-Rokitansky-Küster-Hauser syndrome with magnetic resonance imaging: three patterns of uterine remnants and related anatomical features and clinical settings. *EurRadiol*. 2017;27(12):5215–5224. doi: 10.1007/s00330-017-4919-4
13. Pan HX, Luo GN. Phenotypic and clinical aspects of Mayer-Rokitansky-Küster-Hauser syndrome in a Chinese population: an analysis of 594 patients. *Fertil Steril*. 2016;106(5):1190–1194. doi: 10.1016/j.fertnstert.2016.06.007
14. Oppelt PG, Lermann J, Strick R, et al. Malformations in a cohort of 284 women with Mayer-Rokitansky-Küster-Hauser syndrome (MRKH). *Reprod Biol Endocrinol*. 2012;10(1):57. doi: 10.1186/1477-7827-10-57
15. Heinonen PK. Unicornuate uterus and rudimentary horn. *Fertil Steril*. 1997;68(2):224–230. doi: 10.1016/S0015-0282(97)81506-3
16. Vercellini P, Daguati R, Somigliana E, Viganò P, Lanzani A, Fedele L. Asymmetric lateral distribution of obstructed hemivagina and renal agenesis in women with uterus didelphys: institutional case series and a systematic literature review. *Fertil Steril*. 2007;87:719–24.
17. Smith NA, Laufer MR. Obstructed hemivagina and ipsilateral renal anomaly (OHVIRA) syndrome: management and follow-up. *Fertil Steril*. 2007;87:918–22.
18. Troiano RN, McCarthy SM. Müllerian duct anomalies: imaging and clinical issues. *Radiology*. 2004;233:19–34.
19. Fedele L, Ferrazzi E, Dorta M, Vercellini P, Candiani GB. Ultrasonography in the differential diagnosis of ‘double’ uteri. *Fertil Steril*. 1988;50:361–4.
20. Candiani GB, Ferrazzi E, Fedele L, Vercellini P, Dorta M. Sonographic evaluation of uterine morphology: a new scanning technique. *Acta Eur Fertil*. 1986;17:345–8.
21. Salim R, Jurkovic D. Assessing congenital uterine anomalies: the role of three-dimensional ultrasonography. *Best Pract Res Clin ObstetGynaecol*. 2004;18:29–36.
22. Wu MH, Hsu CC, Huang KE. Detection of congenital müllerian duct anomalies using three-dimensional ultrasound. *J Clin Ultrasound*. 1997;25:487–92.
23. Haddad B, Louis-Sylvestre C, Poitout P, Paniel BJ. Longitudinal vaginal septum: a retrospective study of 202 cases. *Eur J ObstetGynecolReprod Biol*. 1997;74:197–9.
24. Nawroth F, Rahimi G, Nawroth C, Foth D, Ludwig M, Schmidt T. Is there an association between septate uterus and endometriosis? *Hum Reprod*. 2006;21:542–4.
25. The American Fertility Society classification of adnexal adhesions, distal tubal occlusion, tubal occlusion secondary to tubal ligation, tubal pregnancies, müllerian anomalies and intrauterine adhesions. *Fertil Steril*. 1988;49:944–55.
26. Braun P, Grau FV, Pons RM, Enguix DP. Is hysterosalpingography able to diagnose all uterine malformations correctly? A retrospective study. *Eur J Radiol*. 2005;53:274–9.
27. Mazouni C, Girard G, Deter R, Haumonte JB, Blanc B, Bretelle F. Diagnosis of müllerian anomalies in adults: evaluation of practice. *Fertil Steril*. 2008;89:219–22.
28. Lin PC, Bhatnagar KP, Nettleton GS, Nakajima ST. Female genital anomalies affecting reproduction. *Fertil Steril*. 2002;78:899–915.
29. Sanfilippo JS, Wakim NG, Schikler KN, Yussman MA. Endometriosis in association with uterine anomaly. *Am J Obstet Gynecol*. 1986;154:39–43.
30. Raga F, Bauset C, Remohi J, Bonilla-Musoles F, Simon C, Pellicer A. Reproductive impact of congenital müllerian anomalies. *Hum Reprod*. 1997;12:2277–81
31. Kupesic S, Kurjac A, Skenderovic S, Bjelos D. Screening for uterine abnormalities by three-

- dimensional ultrasound improves perinatal outcomes. *J Perinat Med*. 2002;30:9–17.
32. Acien P. Reproductive performance of women with uterine malformations. *Hum Reprod*. 1993;8:122–6.
 33. Ludmir J, Samuels P, Brooks S, Mennuti MT. Pregnancy outcome of patients with uncorrected uterine anomalies managed in a high-risk obstetric setting. *Obstet Gynecol*. 1990;75:906–10.
 34. Saravelos SH, Cocksedge KA, Li TC. Prevalence and diagnosis of congenital uterine anomalies in women with reproductive failure: a critical appraisal. *Hum Reprod Update*. 2008;14:415–29.
 35. Nicolini U, Bellotti M, Bonazzi B, Zamberletti D, Candiani GB. Can ultrasound be used to screen uterine malformations? *Fertil Steril*. 1987;47:89–93.
 36. Caliskan E, Ozkan S, Cakiroglu Y, Sarisoy HT, Corakci A, Ozeren S. Diagnostic accuracy of real-time 3D sonography in the diagnosis of congenital müllerian anomalies in high-risk patients with respect to the phase of the menstrual cycle. *J Clin Ultrasound*. 2010;38:123–7.
 37. Bermejo C, Ten Martinez P, Cantarero R, Diaz D, Perez Pedregosa J, Barron E, et al. Three-dimensional ultrasound in the diagnosis of Müllerian duct anomalies and concordance with magnetic resonance imaging. *Ultrasound Obstet Gynecol*. 2010;35:593–601.
 38. Troiano RN. Magnetic resonance imaging of müllerian duct anomalies of the uterus. *Top Magn Reson Imaging*. 2003;14:269–79.
 39. Jurkovic D, Geipel A, Gruboeck K, Jauniaux E, Natucci M, Campbell S. Three-dimensional ultrasound for the assessment of uterine anatomy and detection of congenital anomalies: a comparison with hysterosalpingography and two-dimensional sonography. *Ultrasound Obstet Gynecol*. 1995;5:233–7.
 40. Raine-Fenning N, Fleischer AC. Clarifying the role of three-dimensional transvaginal sonography in reproductive medicine: an evidence-based appraisal. *J Exp Clin Assist Reprod*. 2005;2:10.
 41. Oppelt P, von Have M, Paulsen M, Strissel PL, Strick R, Brucker S, et al. Female genital malformations and their associated abnormalities. *Fertil Steril*. 2007;87:335–42.
 42. Reichman DE, Laufer MR. Congenital uterine anomalies affecting reproduction. *Best Pract Res Clin ObstetGynaecol*. 2010;24:193–208.